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PLANNING BASED ON CRISIS RESPONSE CAPABILITIES THAT THREATEN UKRAINE'S NATIONAL SECURITY

Annotation. *The research, based on scientific and practical views, proposes the development of basic approaches to planning the activities of military formations and law enforcement agencies, based on the crisis response capabilities that threaten Ukraine's national security and that arise, including in the northern territories.*

Keywords: *planning, crisis response, national security, military formations, security and defense sector.*

1. Introduction

Today, Ukraine is gradually increasing its capacity to counter the aggressive Russian hybrid threat. As noted by M. Pashkov: "Despite the efforts of the Ukrainian authorities to peacefully resolve the conflict, the actions of official Kyiv lack strategic approaches, complexity, effectiveness and consistency" [1]. In addition, there is no doubt that any security issues are relevant to Ukraine, and further development and overall success of the state is impossible without solving the problem of forming crisis

response systems that threaten national security in the system components of the security and defense sector.

2. Literature data analysis and problem statement

The current legislation places the main functions of national security on the security and defense sector, thus forming a set of requirements for crisis response that threatens national security.

As noted by the researcher A.E. Ivanova: "Over the years of the Ukrainian state's existence, work has been done to reform the security and defense sector; it represents the security sector system, its components, what mechanisms of interaction within the system"[2, p. 34].

It also emphasized the lack of control over the processes of development, unsystematic and irrational allocation of resources, the possibility of significant contradictions, confrontation of power structures. [2, p. 35]

On the other hand, to solve these problems, modern science outlines the theoretical and legal foundations of strategic development planning and the necessary capabilities of the security and defense sector identified the need for rational allocation of tasks and responsibilities for specific areas [3].

Issues related to: "topical" threats to national security, as well as "existing" and "potential" threats are subject to resolution [4].

Therefore, it should be acknowledged that the transition to crisis-based planning that threatens Ukraine's national security, including those in the northern territories, is a way of addressing these problems.

3. Research goals and objectives

The purpose of the study is to develop basic approaches to planning the activities of military formations and law enforcement agencies on the basis of crisis response capabilities that threaten Ukraine's national security.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were solved:

- to substantiate the methodology and approaches to the development of a model of activity of military formations and law enforcement agencies on the basis of the capacity to respond to crisis situations that threaten the national security of Ukraine;

- take into account in the parameters of the model of activity of military formations and law enforcement agencies on the basis of the capabilities to respond to crisis situations that threaten the national security of Ukraine features of national security.

4. Methodology and approaches to planning the activities of military formations and law enforcement agencies on the basis of crisis response capabilities that threaten Ukraine's national security

In the Strategic Defense Bulletin 2016, the concept of "capability" is used solely for the purpose of resolving armed conflicts by military means, thus encompassing: "quantitative and qualitative indicators that characterize the ability of the constituent forces of defense to perform their assigned tasks of defense of the state and repulsion of weapons available state capabilities"[5]. At the same time, as the authors of the monograph "The Security and Defense Sector of Ukraine: Theory, Strategy, Practice" point out their analysis revealed that there is no common vision of the problem of capacity building and ways of its solution [3]. They endorsed the position outlined in

the Australian Defense Force's guide to defining the ability to "be conditioned by certain resources and the ability to achieve measurable results when performing a task under specified conditions in accordance with defined standards" [6]. Note that most of the "standards" referred to in this source and other similar documents concern only military security issues and the coordination of algorithms for warfare.

For their part, the structures of the Minister of Defenses, general staffs of most countries, as well as governments' crisis response practices, use capability-based technology, which is a special feature of developing capabilities to effectively counter threats and risks, both military and non-military, taking into account likely scenarios development of crisis situations in the long term, in particular - 10-15 years. As stated in the Defense Planning Recommendations on the basis of capabilities in the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine and the Armed Forces of Ukraine, such technology is recognized as the main method of defense planning [7].

These Guidelines provide for the use in the planning of the activity of any structure of a single terminology, principles and objectives, the procedure for applying certain procedures, monitoring and capacity development. Another important aspect of technology implementation is the gradual transition to the appropriate methodology in the defense planning process.

Capability-based planning involves performing a functional analysis, during which the functions and tasks to be performed are transformed into requirements for capabilities, on the basis of which their creation, maintenance and development are planned [7].

At the same time, experts from the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine insist that the transition to capability-based planning, as opposed to threat-based planning, will ensure that efforts are focused not on creating new organizational structures, but on developing the capabilities of forces (troops) to effectively accomplish certain tasks [7]. Accordingly, in full agreement with these statements, it should be noted that this approach may well be extended to security forces, and the "functional capability groups" established are the same for the security and defense sectors as a whole. Therefore, the central executive authorities, identified in the Law of Ukraine "On National Security of Ukraine" as authorized to lead the security and defense sector, based on capability-based planning methodologies, should enshrine such a unity of approaches in the relevant regulations, and the National Security Council and defense - to initiate the development of a common legal act that would contain a single description of crisis response functions (capabilities) that threaten national security as integrated categories of security, including the activities of various supranational security entities (EU, NATO, etc.).

The functional groups identified (integrated categories) in combination with NATO terminology may be:

- ensuring preparedness for crisis response that threatens national security (complies with FORCE SUPPORT); - covers institutional capacity for leadership at the level of ministries and agencies, military authorities, preparing for crisis response to national security, generating forces, staffing and social protection of personnel and their families;

- cooperation in the field of crisis response that threatens national security (corresponds to PREPARE); of the forces and means, as well as of the forces and means of citizens who voluntarily join and unite to ensure national security;

- deployment and mobility of forces and resources (PROJECT compliant) - covers capabilities of delivery facilities, training of forces (troops) to deploy / transfer to crisis response areas threatening national security, and organization of bases in these areas, taking into account specified readiness periods ;

- application (complies with ENGAGE) - covers the capabilities of forces (troops) to perform basic crisis response tasks that threaten national security, both on their own and within interdepartmental groups, in conjunction with the population and civic associations;

- security (SUSTAIN compliant) - covers capabilities in the field of combat, logistics, technical and medical support for the uniform requirements and in accordance with the standards of international organizations in the field of human rights;

- command and control (consistent with CONSULT, COMMAND & CONTROL) - covers the capabilities of strategic, operational and tactical levels of governing bodies to manage the use of forces (troops) in conjunction with the activities of civil-military administrations when they are formed;

- protection and survivability (PROTECT compliant) - encompasses capabilities to provide protection against threats of natural, man-made, social or military origin and / or active counteraction to local populations;

- situation analysis and its intelligence (corresponds to INFORM) - covers the ability to monitor changes in crisis situations that threaten national security at any level (strategic, operational and tactical) of command and military command;

- military-political leadership, resource management (CORPORATE MANAGEMENT & SUPPORT) - covers institutional capacity for the establishment of civil-military administrations, regulatory support, audit, inspection and comprehensive evaluation (reviews), strategy development, capability planning, organization procurement, software and resource management, budget planning and accounting.

It should be emphasized that each of the proposed functional groups of capabilities during the analysis should be detailed, in particular, it concerns the levels of management (command), grouping (forming subgroups) of capabilities, determining individual measures for their maintenance, upgrading (modernization).

The tasks set out need to address the issue of 'capabilities' for the security and defense sector in general, the security and defense forces separately, the individual components of the security and defense sector, individual units and some military or law enforcement personnel in crisis response that threaten national security. At the same time, as pointed out by both domestic [8] and foreign experts [9], the "capabilities" themselves have certain properties, such as complexity, versatility, adaptability, poor formalization.

Regarding the first of these, it should be noted that such planning activity is mainly concerned not with capacity as a whole, but with its individual component (tasks, standards, conditions, forces and means) and its impact on other components. Therefore, it can be summarized that the quantitative characterization of crisis response capabilities that threaten national security is determined by the number of tasks assigned to the entities responsible for the security and defense sector management and included in the content of the relevant decisions.

At the same time, most of these decisions are distinguished by a high degree of versatility and uncertainty as to what forces and means should be involved in crisis response that threatens national security in the event of certain conditions.

Assume that with the development of security forces, the fulfillment of most of the crisis response tasks that threaten national security will provide the same composition of forces and resources in different projected situations. At the same time, these forces and means will necessarily possess the adaptability of their capabilities - the ability to build, complement, combine with other abilities in the conditions of modification or complication of the tasks in existing situations of response or in the case of new tasks in a rapidly changing environment.

Another important prediction is the recognition at the legislative level of the impossibility of describing capabilities solely on formal grounds regarding the development of human resources, and therefore, the refusal of competitive selection for positions in the security forces and its replacement by employment contracts with individual conditions for capacity expansion. The solution to this problem should be concurrent with the regulation of processes of increasing the level of "capabilities" (transition of a specialist, unit or body to a new level of "capabilities") as the main direction of improving the activities of military formations and law enforcement agencies in crisis response that threaten national security.

Accordingly, "Catalogs of crisis response capabilities that threaten national security" should be established as a basis for the formation of functional (job) responsibilities of personnel of the security and defense forces and in the traditional linear (linear-functional) structures of the security and defense sector and in project structures formed to respond to a particular crisis.

You should also point to the likely emergence of particular specializations or professions related to crisis response that threaten national security in the National Classifier of Professions. At the same time, consideration should be given to the "alignment" of the security and defense sector, under which each structural unit (element, component) of the security and defense forces, or a combination of forces and assets, confirms the ability to perform certain tasks (to ensure the achievement of certain strategic and operational goals) under certain conditions, resourcing, and according to established standards.

5. Conclusions and results of the study

1. The main tasks to be solved by the means of planning the activities of military formations and law enforcement agencies on the basis of crisis response capabilities that threaten the national security of Ukraine and which arise, including in the northern territories, should be considered:

- assessment of the security environment, defining the principles, goals and main tasks of national policy in the field of crisis response, threatening national security, priorities and directions of the development of security forces and forces, taking into account real and potential threats to national security, demographic and financial and economic opportunities the state;

- determination of requirements for capabilities, structure, number of personnel of military formations and law enforcement agencies, quantitative and qualitative indicators of arms and military (special) equipment, other types of logistics, military (special) infrastructure, preparedness of personnel of security and defense forces ;

- an assessment of the state of readiness of the security and defense forces to fulfill crisis response tasks that threaten national security (assessment of existing capabilities to fulfill the tasks in all identified scenarios), as well as the results of implementation of measures for their development in the previous period;

- the formation of a comprehensive document on the development of capabilities of the security and defense forces and the need to develop their capabilities in expenditures of the State Budget, risk assessment;

- resource planning for security forces and defense forces (formation of proposals for state defense orders, planning of purchases of products, works and services);

- planning of mobilization training activities in the security and defense components;

- organizing the implementation of the tasks and activities of programs and plans, assessing the state of achievement of capabilities.

2. It is advisable to categorize capabilities with the identification of three main groups: operational capabilities, combat capabilities, special capabilities. In responding to national security threats, operational and special capabilities are crucial, which, as a result, will make it possible to relate the forces (troops) they possess to the security forces.

3. Further regulatory support and detailing of the capabilities in the relevant by-laws are required, whereby the authorized bodies must put into effect standards that are specific to the structural unit (element) of each species. In particular, in view of the position of the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine, each structural unit (element) of the defense forces must "receive" more than one combat (special) capability, and each capability must be implemented by more than one structural (unit) element [7].

4. When planning, capabilities should be designated as either necessary or available or critical. "Necessary capabilities for crisis response that threaten national security", as a basis for planning, are those capabilities that have been included in the General Capability Catalog of the authority (unit) and must be permanently available to the appropriate chief (commander) at the designated time and at a designated location, to fulfill national security threats in a specific environment with the desired result (effect). "Existing crisis response capabilities that threaten national security" are those capabilities that are available to the appropriate chief (commander) to complete the tasks but may not be sufficient to achieve the desired result (effect). "Critical crisis response capabilities that threaten national security" are those capabilities that are absolutely essential to achieving the required result (effect) of a crisis response that threatens national security by an appropriate authority (unit) and in need of creation (development) and retention in priority.

5. It is advisable to evaluate the available capabilities in the presence of certain scenarios. Under the following conditions, the following are evaluated:

- the structure and composition of state and law enforcement agencies, existing units of military units regarding their ability to perform tasks for each response situation with the required level of effectiveness;

- the level of preparedness and training of the personnel to perform tasks in the anticipated situations (flight hours, number of tactical exercises conducted, the level of technical readiness in accordance with the norms, etc.), in particular and in accordance with available experience, experience, terms of service, etc .;

- the availability and technical condition of the necessary samples of weapons, military and special equipment to perform tasks in situations taking into account their ability to perform other tasks;

- the state of logistics systems (logistics) to accomplish the task according to situations, in particular the amount of inventory and the ability to replenish and store them in proper conditions;

- the availability of military infrastructure and its ability to support the vital activity of the region and to ensure that certain tasks are fulfilled according to the forecast situations;

- available facilities and certain elements of infrastructure that will be disposed of or that cannot be mobilized when responding to a crisis that threatens national security.

6. The results of the evaluation shall identify certain deviations from existing capabilities from those needed to respond to a crisis that threatens national security. These results are an indicator (indicator) of how significant the difference between the required and available crisis response capabilities that threaten national security is to the security and defense sector.

7. Having identified the difference between required and available capabilities, the needs for material resources should be identified, as well as moving on to assessing capacity development risks and assessing performance based on capabilities.

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